

KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS ON APPLICATION OF 3D DESIGNING AND PRINTING AMONGST DENTAL PRACTITIONERS IN CENTRAL INDIA- A QUESTIONNAIRE BASED SURVEY

Dr. Sayali Nikode¹, Dr. Jaykumar Gade², Dr. Ravina Khairkar³, Dr. Zehra Rana⁴,
Dr.Roshni Taori⁵, Dr. Shruti Matale⁶

Department of Prosthodontics,

Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur, India

Abstract

Background – The use of 3D Printing is widely trending amongst dentists in every aspect of dentistry, dentistry has been transformed by 3D printing. Its applications include prosthodontic appliances, surgical planning and in making surgical stents, dental implants, aligners, and even study models in addition to 3D imaging. **Aim** – this cross-sectional questionnaire based study aims to assess knowledge and awareness on application of 3d designing and printing amongst dental practitioners in central India. **Methodology** – The study was conducted amongst dental practitioners of central India after clearance in Institutional ethics committee with a sample size of 126. The questionnaire from the study of Dhokar AA was modified and used with due permission of the author in Google Forms, was circulated amongst dental practitioners in central India and the responses were recorded. **Results** – It was seen that males showed significantly better awareness compared to their counterparts ($P<0.05$), but age, education, expertise area, and years in practice did not affect awareness levels significantly. Subjects with master's degrees had significantly higher knowledge levels ($P<0.05$), particularly specialists with master's degrees compared to general practitioners, other specialists, and interns. Age and years in practice did not significantly influence knowledge levels. **Conclusion** – perception into the acceptance and use of 3D printing and designing have been divulged lately within the limitations of the study.

Key words – Dental Practitioners , 3D Printing, Knowledge, Awareness, Questionnaire

I.INTRODUCTION

Dental care has undergone a remarkable evolution with the advent of digital technology, transforming what was once a conventional, two-dimensional approach into the cutting-edge realm of three-dimensional dental practices. This shift, often referred to as 'Digital Dentistry,' has surged in popularity, offering patients a faster, higher-quality treatment experience unlike ever before. One such transformative technology is the use of 3D printers, which is set to completely revolutionize the manufacturing process. In dentistry, the combination of contemporary imaging modalities such as intra-oral scanners^{1,2} and cone beam computed tomography (CBCT)³ with 3D printing has demonstrated encouraging outcomes.⁴ With the use of this technology, dental professionals may now produce accurate crown copings, partial denture frameworks, full mouth rehabilitation, diagnostic models, castings, and digital implantology and Prosthodontics.⁵⁻⁷ but as the new technology is introduced to reach its awareness it takes time. Therefore this study aims to assess knowledge and awareness of 3D Printing and Designing amongst dental professionals. However, whenever new technology is introduced, increasing awareness among professionals takes time. Therefore, this study aims to assess the knowledge and awareness of 3D printing and designing among dental professionals in central India.

II.METHODOLOGY –

A. Study design - This is a cross-sectional questionnaire study.

B. Study setting - The study was conducted amongst dental practitioners of central India after clearance in Institutional ethics committee.

C. Sample size – Sample size was determined considering the proportion of having knowledge and awareness on application of 3D designing and printing as the main outcome. A pilot study was conducted on 12 subjects 75% were having above average knowledge on application of 3d designing and printing. For 99% confidence interval with 10% absolute precession a sample size of 126 is considered sufficient to estimate true parameter values in the target population.

D. Sampling method - A random sample of 125 subjects who fulfilled eligibility criteria and consented to participate in this survey were selected from a sampling frame available from dental practitioners of central India including graduates (BDS) and postgraduates (MDS).

E. Study method – A specially created web designed survey in Google forms was circulated among Dental Practitioners of central India and their responses were recorded. A Pilot study was conducted first, and changes needed were done in the questionnaire according to the responses.

The questionnaire from study by Dhokar AA⁸ was modified and used with due permission of the author for this study which includes 6 demographic questions and 19 close-ended questions related to knowledge and awareness on application of 3D Designing and Printing amongst dental practitioners of central India.

The Inclusion and Exclusion criteria are described in Table 1.

Table 1 – Inclusion and Exclusion criteria.	
Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria –
Dental Practitioners of central India.	Non-Dental practitioners.
BDS and MDS, General clinical Practitioners.	Dental practitioners other than in central India.

F. Data analysis – Data was coded and analysed in a statistical software STATA Version 10.1 2011 by stata Corp, Texas, USA. This is a descriptive study where percentage of subjects having knowledge and awareness on application of 3d Designing and Printing was estimated along with 95% confidence interval.

The t-test for 2 independent samples was used to compare means and Pearson's Chi-square test was used to compare proportions in knowledge and awareness amongst dental practitioners of central India. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

III.RESULTS

The study encompassed 126 participants from different dental specialties shown in fig.1 and table 1, revealing that age did not exert a significant influence on either awareness or knowledge levels. While gender has significant influence on awareness levels ($p = 0.045$), with higher awareness among males (93.4%) compared to females (81.5%), it did not have a

significant effect on knowledge levels ($p = 0.831$), where proportions of knowledgeable individuals were similar between males (55.7%) and females (53.9%).

Educational background emerged as a pivotal factor, with individuals holding Master's degrees demonstrating significantly greater levels of both awareness (91.3%) and knowledge (65.2%) than those with Bachelor's degrees (awareness: 82.5%, knowledge: 42.1%). The differences were statistically significant for knowledge ($p = 0.009$) but not for awareness ($p = 0.138$), underscoring the impact of higher educational attainment on deeper understanding.

Additionally, specialization within the field significantly influenced both awareness ($p = 0.089$) and knowledge ($p = 0.017$). Specialists and those with advanced training exhibited notably higher awareness (60.0%) and knowledge (66.0%) compared to generalists and interns (awareness: 37.5%, knowledge: 45.6%). This highlights the advantage of specialized knowledge and professional experience in enhancing comprehension and proficiency.

Conversely, the number of years in practice did not show statistically significant differences in either awareness ($p = 0.685$) or knowledge ($p = 0.062$). This suggests that while practical experience contributes to skills development, it may not uniformly correlate with theoretical understanding or awareness levels in this context.

In conclusion, while age and gender displayed varying impacts on awareness and knowledge, educational attainment and specialization emerged as consistent predictors of heightened awareness and deeper knowledge. These findings underscore the multifaceted influence of demographic factors in shaping understanding and underscore the importance of targeted educational pathways and specialized training in fostering comprehensive expertise across diverse dental populations.

Table 1. Distribution of subjects according to Area of expertise of subjects

Area of expertise	No.	%
Endodontic	3	2.38
General dentist	48	38.10
Intern	5	3.97
Master in public health	1	0.79
Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeon	21	16.67
Orthodontics	23	18.25
Periodontist	1	0.79
Periodontology	1	0.79
Prosthodontics	22	17.46
Any other please specify	1	0.79
Total	126	100

Comparison of proportions/means of subjects with correct awareness by their demographic characteristics

Characteristics	Awareness		P value
	Yes	NO	
Age			
Mean (SD)	27.4 (3.1) years	26.6 (2.6) years	0.3335, Not Significant
Gender			
Male	57 (93.4%)	4 (6.6%)	0.045, Significant
Female	53 (81.5%)	12 (18.5%)	
Education			
Bachelors	47 (82.5%)	10 (17.5%)	0.138, Not Significant
Masters	63 (91.3%)	6 (8.7%)	
Expertise			
General/Interns/Others	6 (37.5%)	10 (62.5%)	0.089, Not Significant
Masters/Specialists	66 (60.0%)	44 (40.0%)	
No. of years in practice			
≥ 5 years	21 (38.9%)	33 (61.1%)	0.685, Not Significant
< 5 years	5 (45.5%)	6 (54.5%)	

Comparison of proportions/means of subjects with correct knowledge by their demographic characteristics			
Characteristics	Knowledge		P value
	Yes	NO	
Age			
Mean (SD)	27.5 (2.4) years	27.0 (2.9) years	0.3396, Not Significant
Gender			
Male	34 (55.7%)	27 (44.3%)	0.831, Not Significant
Female	35 (53.9%)	30 (46.1%)	
Education			
Bachelors	24 (42.1%)	33 (57.9%)	0.009, Significant
Masters	45 (65.2%)	24 (34.8%)	
Expertise			
General/Interns/Others	26 (45.6%)	31 (54.4%)	0.017 Significant
Masters/Specialists	46 (66.0%)	23 (33.3%)	
No. of years in practice			
≥ 5 years	15 (46.9%)	17 (53.1%)	0.062, Not Significant
< 5 years	23 (69.7%)	10 (30.3%)	

IV.DISCUSSION

3D printing, originally pioneered by Charles Hull in the 1980s with his invention of "stereolithography" (SL)⁹, is a revolutionary manufacturing technique. 3D printing is also known as Additive manufacturing / Rapid prototyping¹⁰ operates under the principle of additive manufacturing. It is a computer generated process in which successive layers of materials are added to create 3D objects.⁸ Additive manufacturing is gaining popularity in the dental field, where it is being used for everything from printing surgical guides for implants to creating anatomical models, bio-printing, and systems like Invisalign that offer an attractive alternative to labial fixed appliances by creating a series of custom-made clear aligners for orthodontics.¹¹⁻¹³

This study indicates that practitioners in central India generally have a reasonable awareness of the applications of 3D printing and designing, as evidenced by the absence of significant differences in most criteria, except for a notable distinction between males and females ($P < 0.05$). Interestingly, factors such as age, education level, area of expertise, and years of professional experience showed no statistically significant influence on the awareness levels of the study participants.

Regarding knowledge, it was found that a significantly higher proportion of subjects with Master's degrees possessed correct knowledge compared to those without ($P < 0.05$). Specifically, specialists with Master's degrees demonstrated a markedly higher level of knowledge compared to general practitioners, interns, or those in other specialty areas. Age and years of practice, however, did not significantly affect the knowledge levels of the study subjects.

Further analysis revealed that 74.6% of the individuals surveyed had knowledge about the working principles of 3D printing, while only 56.35% were aware of the most common file format used for 3D printing. Moreover, a mere 42.06% of respondents knew the correct sequence for generating a prototype for 3D printing, despite 80.95% correctly identifying different types of 3D printing methods. Moreover, approximately 48.4% of respondents demonstrated knowledge about the cost-effectiveness of 3D printing, being able to accurately comment on the most expensive and cheapest types of 3D printers.

In conclusion, despite existing literature on the applications of 3D printing in dentistry, the study highlights that practitioners' actual knowledge remains inadequate for its routine utilization in practice. This underscores a need for enhanced education and training initiatives to bridge this gap and better integrate 3D printing technologies into dental practices effectively.

V.LIMITATIONS

The sample size of 126 is not fully representative of population of dental practitioners in central India. Due to voluntary participation response bias cannot be eliminated. Also it is being not accessible to those who cannot be reached via emails or social platform. The study population only considered the practitioners from central India.

Further research can focus on evaluating the clinical outcome and cost effectiveness from patients point of view. Diagnostic ease, treatment outcomes, and prognosis associated with the use of 3D printed models or appliances in dentistry. Conducting studies on a larger, nationwide sample would offer valuable insights into integrating this technology into routine dental practice.

VI.CONCLUSION

The findings from our questionnaire-based survey highlight a significant gap in knowledge and awareness regarding the application of 3D designing and printing among dental practitioners in Central India. Addressing these gaps through targeted education and training initiatives is crucial to harnessing the full potential of this technology in advancing dental practice in the region. Increased awareness and proficiency in 3D designing and printing can ultimately enhance treatment outcomes and patient care, positioning Central India's dental community at the forefront of innovative dental technologies.

QUESTIONNAIRE

- ⇒ Age (years)
- ⇒ Gender
- ⇒ Educational qualification

- Bachelor of dental surgery
- Masters of dental surgery

- ⇒ Area of expertise
 - Prosthodontics
 - Orthodontics
 - Oral and Maxillofacial Surgeon
 - General dentist
 - Any Other Please Specify

- ⇒ No of years in practice

1. Are you aware about the use of 3d printing in dentistry?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not sure
2. Has its awareness and use in dentistry increased recently?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not sure
3. In what ways would you like to gain a deeper understanding of 3D printing?
 - Workshops
 - Seminars
 - Demonstrations
 - All of the above
 - Not sure

4. What is 3d printing?
 - 3D printing is the automated process of building a three-dimensional object by adding material rather than taking material away.
 - 3D printing is the automated process of building a three-dimensional object by subtracting material rather than adding material.
 - Not sure
5. How does 3d printing works?
 - Subtractive manufacturing
 - Additive manufacturing
 - Not sure
6. What are the types of 3D Printing?
 - Selective laser melting (SLM)
 - Fused deposition modeling (FDM)
 - Stereolithography (SLA)
 - Material jetting (MJ)
 - All of the above
7. Which of the following is not an example of additive manufacturing?
 - Fused deposition modelling
 - Electron beam machining
 - SLS
 - Injection moulding
8. Carving, drilling, milling and chiselling are all examples of what?
 - Additive manufacturing
 - Subtractive manufacturing
 - Cutting
 - Forming
9. What are the most common 3d printing file formats?
 - STL
 - OBJ
 - PLY
 - 3MF
 - Not sure
10. STL stands for
 - Support Triangulation Language
 - Standard Tessellation Language
 - Standard Template Language
 - None of above
11. Choose the correct sequence to generate prototype.
 - 3D CAD data - CAD solid model - STL file - RP prototype
 - STL file - 3D CAD data - CAD solid model - RP prototype
 - CAD solid model - 3D CAD data - RP prototype - STL file
 - 3D CAD data - STL file - CAD solid model - RP prototype
12. Which of the following technologies is capable of printing metal?
 - Fused deposition modeling (FDM)
 - Stereolithography (SLA)
 - Material jetting (MJ)
 - Selective laser melting (SLM)
13. Which of the following is the most expensive and cheapest type of 3D printer?
 - a)SLM and FFF
 - b)SLA and FFF
 - c)SLM and LOM
 - d)SLM and SGC
14. What is the full form of SLS
 - Selective Layer Sintering
 - Selective Laser Sintering
 - Selective lithographic solution
 - Specified Laser Sintering
15. What requirements do you believe are necessary for the successful use of 3D printers?
 - Intraoral scanners
 - Casts and models
 - CBCT
 - CAD machine
 - All of the above
 - Not sure

16. What do you consider to be the best material for 3D printing?
- Light cure biocompatible resin
 - UV resin
 - Methacrylic oligomers
 - Hybrid composite resin
 - Acrylic photopolymer
 - Not sure.
17. what do you think are the mandatory applications of 3D printers?(multiple response allowed)
- surgical stents for guidance in dental implants.
 - Crown and bridge fabrication
 - Drill templates and guides in calcified pulp canals in RCT.
 - Digital Orthodontics (invisalign aligners and night guards)
 - Partial denture framework.
 - Pre-surgical assessment/ planning for maxillofacial reconstruction surgeries.
 - Not sure.
18. What considerations you must make when choosing a 3D printing technology?
Tick all that apply.
- Material
 - Durability
 - Melting point
 - Surface finish
 - Focus group input
 - Time
 - Detail
 - Application
19. In your opinion, is 3D Printing cost effective?
- Yes
 - No
 - Not sure

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